

Notes relative to the treatment of Rubiaceae tribe VIII. Coffeeae in *Flore d'Afrique centrale*

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In these notes I explain some of the taxonomic decisions made for the treatment of some Coffeeae taxa in *Flore d'Afrique centrale* (Robbrecht et al. 2024), the rationale being too long for being included in the *Flore* itself. BR barcode numbers of specimens are given to allow rapid access to images in the virtual herbarium of BR (<https://www.botanicalcollections.be>).

1. The *Empogona filiformistipulata* complex

Some *Empogona* species are characterized by a dimorphic type of indumentum on the young stems, the petioles and the nerves on the lower side of the leaf-blade. They have long hairs placed in-between a dense cover of very short erect hairs (illustrated in Robbrecht 1979: fig. 28C). The feature is restricted to only four species, *Empogona welwitschii*, *E. talbotii*, *E. filiformistipulata* and “*Tricalysia landanensis*” (combination under *Empogona* not available).

E. welwitschii is well discernible by its triangular calyx lobes and large number of ovules, (8)10–13 per placenta; its relationship with the ill known *T. landanensis* from Angola remains, however, to be clarified (see Robbrecht 1979: 355). *E. filiformistipulata* has rounded to subacute calyx lobes and only 3–5 ovules per placenta. *E. talbotii* has features in between: rounded calyx lobes and (1)2–8 ovules per placenta. In my revision I stressed the close relationship between the latter two species, stating that they “perhaps represent only one species with several infraspecific categories” (Robbrecht 1979: 354). I then refrained from synonymy because only scant material was available. During a visit to the herbarium P (in 1983) I observed that a large number of specimens of the complex was not included in the loans for my revision. Further new material gathered during the intensive prospections in Cameroon and Gabon during the last decades is also available. The complex is barely in need of a new revision and likely contains novelties to be delimited and described. *Urophyllum insculptum* Hutch. & Dalz. (*Pauridiantha insculpta* (Hutch. & Dalz.) Bremek.) from Nigeria (holotype Oban, Talbot s.n., K) is in fact a species of *Empogona* also belonging to this complex, and should be considered during the necessary new revision.

The following features should inter alia be evaluated for diagnostic importance: base of the leaf-blades (cuneate, rounded or cordate), hairiness of the leaves, number of ovules per placenta, from only 2 to more than 10, style (glabrous or hairy), and carpological characters. In some specimens I observed seeds partly covered by an outgrowth of the placenta, a feature in the genus only known from *E. breteleri*. I also have seen, in only two specimens, a seed type not met with in any other species of *Empogona*. The two seeds of a locule are horizontally placed above one another (figure 1), unlike the seeds in vertical juxtaposition of other *Empogona* species with a low number of ovules per placenta. The helmet-like appearance of the seeds, with a flat contact zone, obviously is caused by place constraints, as confirmed by the embryo position. The latter can be deduced from the subsidence in the seed-coat at the place of the radicle – basal in the two seeds despite their inverted shape. An aborted placenta in the second locule of a fruit with two superposed seeds showed the

two ovules already in a superposed position; less scant material is needed for full comprehension of this peculiar carpological condition.

Also, my 1979 revision divided *E. filiformistipulata* in two infraspecies because of differences in leaf indumentum. A specimen (Cameroon, J.J.F.E. de Wilde 7699; not seen for the 1979 revision) intermediate in this respect casts doubt on that distinction. Because of this, I have no longer kept infraspecific taxa under *E. filiformistipulata* in the treatment in the *Flore*.

A side note: the suggested presence of *E. filiformistipulata* in Côte d'Ivoire (Robbrecht 1979: 351) was confirmed by Aké Assi (2002: 105).

2. An *Empogona* indet. from the Maniema

The historical specimen A.L. Berger s.n. (BR0000019687636; specimen image with drawings of dissection) belongs to *Empogona*. It misses a collector's label and just bears a stamp "Coll. Berger 1909". Berger worked in R.D. Congo from 1906 to 1909, and made a collection when active in the area conceded to the "Comité special du Katanga"; his specimens are considered to come from the Maniema, a region on the border of the Central Forest and the Lower Katanga District (E 26–29°, S 2–5°). The collection is in young fruiting stage and reminds *Empogona breteleri* in having 1–2 seeds per locule partly covered by a placental outgrowth. The specimen differs from *E. breteleri* inter alia in having tuft domatia. It is too poor to allow a conclusion. The Maniema is distinctly away from the Lower Guinean area of *E. breteleri*.

3. *Empogona nogueirae* in Kasai

A historical specimen from the Kwango area, Kasai, R.D. Congo, collected in December 1945 (Renier 108; BR0000009938656), was filed in the indet. Rubiaceae, and I missed it for my revision of *Tricalysia* subsp. *Empogona* (Robbrecht 1979). In 1987, I tentatively identified it as *Tricalysia* cf. *glabra* (*Empogona glabra*), but even had doubt with regard to the generic position because of three odd characters not known for *Empogona*: an articulation on top of the pedicel, two horn-like recurved structures at the base of the calyculus, and anthers sagittate at base (figure 2). The first two might represent deformations caused by an external factor. I did not explicitly report sagittate anthers from *Empogona*, but my drawing of *Empogona nogueirae* (Robbrecht 1979: fig. 25) shows that it is the case for that species. Renier reported the corolla colour of its collection ("fleurs rouges"), and reddish flowers too are a feature of *E. nogueirae*. The Renier specimen also matches *E.*

nogueirae in the size of its corollas, relatively large for *Empogona*, in the internal hairiness of the corolla tube, not rising above the throat as in most *Empogona* species, and in the ovules, horseshoe-like positioned at the margin of the placenta. I now believe that this collection is the only documenting the presence of *E. nogueirae* in R.D. Congo.

Figure 2. Dissection of a flower of the Renier 108 specimen. From left to right: flower bud; portion of its corolla, laid open longitudinally to show internal hairs and stamen insertion; style and stigma; ovary and calyx, two lobes removed to show disk; ovary and calyx surrounded by calyculus bearing appendages at its base; stamens; placentas with ovules. Scales = 1 mm, except for flower bud and style (= 5 mm).

E. glabra and *E. nogueirae* are a pair of sibling species, the first shrubby and the second generally geofrutescent. Their distribution is \pm sympatric, but the area of the geofrutex is more restricted and linked to drier habitats such as sandy soils. The distribution of *E. nogueirae* in Angola is centred in the Bié plateau, but the species is also reported from Cuanza Norte, i.e. not far away from the Congo locality. The high plateaus of the Kwango area are covered with Kalahari sands (see Lubini 2001); the habitat required by the geofrutescent *E. nogueirae* is hence present in the Kwango area.

4. *Belonophora hypoglauca*

In a short revision of *Belonophora*, Cheek & Dawson (2000) concluded that *Belonophora hypoglauca*, a species widespread on the African mainland, should be reduced to synonymy of *Belonophora coffeoides*, a species from Sao Tomé only known from the type. This had already been suggested by Chevalier in 1939. Cheek & Dawson advocated that some minor features probably allow to distinguish the island populations from the mainland taxon, viz. the generally smaller leaves and the longer stipules. This way they “saved” the epithet *hypoglauca* in recognizing the mainland species as a subspecies of *B. coffeoides*.

This does not hold with the variation of the numerous specimens from R.D. Congo that I have examined in BR. Table 1 compares my measurements with the type of Sao Tomé (image available in the online herbarium of Kew). The specimens are too differently composed for a detailed biometrical study, so I decided to measure the longest stipule and the largest leaf (its petiole, length, width and acumen; table 1) on each R.D Congo specimen. I made the same measurements on a syntype of *B. coffeoides* available online. The graph (figure 3) shows that the type of *B. coffeoides* falls very well within the variation of the Congo specimens. It is therefore not justified to recognize subspecies based on that evidence.

The sole specimen from the Upper Katanga District, *Van Meel 1884*, puzzled me too because of its stipules longer than in any other specimen. It seems the extreme of the trend to long stipular awns. Also, it comes from the northernmost part of the District (surroundings of Kalemie), i.e. close to the records in the VI and IX Districts, so is not geographically isolated.

Table 1. Leaf variation (in mm) in "*Belonophora hypoglauca*" in R.D. Congo, compared to the type of *Belonophora coffeoides* (Mann) from Sao Tomé.

	petiole	blade length	blade width	acumen	stipule
Gérard 586	10	120	42	10	7
Gérard 643	12	145	47	14	11
Hart 887	13	160	42	20	7
Luja s.n. 873193	10	163	50	10	5
Claessens 618	8	165	48	13	7
Claessens 1	9	170	61	12	11
Hart 887	10	170	40	17	7
Gérard 2678	8	170	62	13	7
Batido 4	13	175	54	20	10
Gutzwiller 1213	8	180	60	12	9
Troupin 12458	10	180	70	13	8
Pauwels 4268	10	185	55	20	9
Germain 5197	10	187	65	11	18
Gillet s.n. (type <i>B. gilletii</i>)	9	190	80	8	10
Germain 7983	9	190	83	5	5
De Witte 13008	13	190	64	10	11
Dewulf 219	10	190	76	10	7
Hart 360	9	193	70	16	8
Dewulf 593	10	195	63	12	16
Hart 360	12	195	70	18	8
Gilbert 2113	15	195	58	15	8
Troupin 1022	12	195	68	10	10
Mann (type <i>B. coffeoides</i>)	10	200	60	18	15
Masens 689	13	210	60	10	18
Troupin 6381	16	210	58	15	13
Luke 141781	19	210	92	14	10
Liengola 121	17	218	65	14	22
Gereau et al, 5239	12	220	63	18	15
Gérard 2742	14	220	80	12	8
Devred 2886	14	225	83	10	10
Van Meel 1884	11	230	73	18	26
Lebrun 5843	15	245	80	10	9
Evrard 634	13	250	73	14	12
Leclercq 381	11	260	110	20	

Figure 3.
Graph of measurements in table 1.

Cheek & Dawson (2000) cited Mann 1860 as the holotype of *B. coffeoides*, but it seems that they confused the collection year with the number. The online herbarium of Kew provides images of two specimens Mann 1059 (figure 4). There is no evidence that the two sheets were collected from the same tree, although this is probable. They should be regarded as syntypes, and the 347030 designated as lectotype (I have formally done so in the *Flore*).

Figure 4. Mann specimens numbered 1059 in K (online herbarium of K).
 K00347030: with Mann's original label and an institutional label for the Mann collection received 1861; the empty parts of the sheet are provided with detailed pencil drawings of a dissection, apparently made by Hiern for his Flora of Tropical Africa treatment.
 K00347031: with only (the same) institutional label, with pencil addition "1059 Coffea".

5. *Sericanthe* in the Kwango (Kasaï)

The Kwango area in the Kasai, southern R.D. Congo is floristically poorly known. The area, with a topography from 450 to 1050 m, adjacent to Northern Angola, has a richly diversified vegetation, a mosaic with several types of forest, savanna and steppe (see Devred 1957, Devred et al. 1958) and its flora comprises Guineo-Congolian as well as Zambezian elements. It is floristically poorly prospected.

For my revision of *Sericanthe* (Robbrecht 1978), only two specimens from the Kwango were available, Devred 2265 and 2205, collected in the framework of the above cited vegetation studies of this collector. In my revision, Devred 2265 (BR0000006414863), from a marshy forest type, was considered to belong to the Guineo-Congolian taxon *Sericanthe testui* var. *testui*, although it shows slight differences such as the stipules having a thinner texture. Its occurrence in the Kwango is some 1000 km away from the main area in Gabon. The Kwango population hence perhaps merits separate recognition, but more material should be available.

Devred 2205 (BR0000019441337), from a forest on the Kwango Plateau, is very different, e.g. by the very slender branches and the thin and small leaves. In my revision, it was cited with the unnamed specimens and marked as a possible new species. Almost fifty years later, it remains represented by this sole collection. To attract attention to its existence, I now judge it better to recognize it formally as a species. The collection Devred 2205 comprises flower bases (corolla and androecium fallen off) and fruits, and this allows to confirm its belonging to *Sericanthe* and to find diagnostic features for its recognition. The formal naming (*Sericanthe kwangoensis*), illustration and description is in the *Flore* itself. The affinity is with the montane species *S. leonardii* from Kivu. The Kwango High Plateau has an elevation up to 1100 m, and *S. kwangoensis* seems to belong to the montane/submontane group of species in *Sericanthe*.

The endemism of the Kwango (and adjacent part of Angola) merits further study. Examples of endemic species are *Eriosema kwangoense* Hauman, *Tricalysia kwangoensis* (Robbr.) Robbr., *Xyris kwangolana* P.A.Duvign. & Homés, *Ganguelia gossweileri* (S.Moore) Robbr.

6. A lianescent *Sericanthe* species from the Ngazi forest

Ngazi forest is adjacent to the north of the Yangambi Biosphere Reserve. In 1939 Louis here collected a lianescent species of *Sericanthe* – his collection number 14827 (3 sheets in BR, BR0000019441306, BR0000019441313, BR0000019441320), labeled “grosse liane de 8 cm de diamètre, retombante au-dessus de l’eau” (figure 5). Despite the fact that the individual was followed up by the then INEAC staff at Yangambi (as observed specimen number 961), no other collections appear to have ever been made. Neither I found conspecific material at the time of my 1978 revision. I then noted (Robbrecht 1978: 23, footnote 3): “Louis 14 827 (BR), collected at Ngazi, in the mud along the Lotembo river ... is undoubtedly a *Sericanthe*. It differs from all other species in being a true liana climbing by recurved branchlets [figure 6] and it comes near *S. raynalianum* by its glabrous ovary, its absence of cecidia [bacterial galls], its leaf shape and its indumentum. As the only collection is in fruit this taxon cannot be described.”

All species of *Sericanthe* occurring in the Flore area belong to subgenus *Sericanthe*, characterized by a shrubby or arborescent habit (one species, *S. suffruticosa*, is geofrutescent); one species (*S. testui*) is occasionally reported to be lianescent (Letouzey 10142, BR0000006915544). Subgenus *Macrocarpus* (recognized later, Robbrecht 1981) comprises only two species, one from Upper and one from Lower Guinea, both always lianescent. The fruits of the lianescent Ngazi species, further show all features characteristic of subgenus *Sericanthe* (fruits spherical, 1 cm in diam., with leathery pericarp; 2 ¼-spherical seeds in each chamber; seeds with a large elliptic hilar scar and not surrounded by ariloid outgrowth; versus fruits larger, ellipsoidal; pericarp thick and sclerified; 3–5 seeds in each chamber, surrounded by outgrowth in subg. *Macrocarpus*).

Figure 5. Labeled sheet 1 of Louis 14827 (BR0000019441306).

Figure 6. A third sheet of Louis 14827 (BR0000019441313), taken from the duplicates and mounted for BR because it shows recurved branchlets functioning as climbing hooks.

Phytogeographically, the Ngazi species is interesting in that it is the only forest species inhabiting the lowland Congo basin, though the collecting place lies at the northern, more elevated side of the Congo River in Yangambi (see fig. 7).

Fifty eight years after its discovery and 45 years after my revision, the species remains too imperfectly known for formal recognition. For the treatment in the *Flore*, it was even impossible to key it out. I made a note in the heading of the key, referring to a short description at the end of the genus' treatment under the informal name "Ngazi."

7. Two further notes on *Sericanthe*

Sericanthe pellegrinii was hitherto only recorded from Gabon and R.D. Congo (Robbrecht 1978). I now also identified a historical specimen from southern Cameroon: Groß-Batanga, Dinklage 1089 (HBG).

While writing the treatment of *Sericanthe* for the *Flore*, the name *Sericanthe assimilis* Sond. popped up in several consulted databases on the internet, inter alia in GBIF and in Tropicos (accessed 27 October 2022). The name obviously is a computed error combining the component "assimilis Sond." with *Sericanthe*. Apparently *Pavetta assimilis* Sond. (Sonder 1894) was the input source. That name is the only with epithet *assimilis* given to a Rubiaceae species by Sonder – he used the same epithet for two other species, in *Acmadenia* (Rutaceae) and *Cyphia* (Campanulaceae).

8. Intraspecific variation of *Tricalysia coriacea*

Tricalysia coriacea is one of the most widespread species of the genus, occurring from Sierra Leone to Uganda and Tanzania in the east, and to Angola and Mozambique in the south (Robbrecht 1987a: fig. 10B). It is a linking element of Guineo-Congolian and the Zambezan floras. The Dahomey gap is the only interruption of its distribution. The morphological variation is wide, and “at first sight one would distinguish a Guinean taxon with larger, often elliptic or ovate leaf-blades, and a Zambezan one with smaller obovate leaf-blades” (Robbrecht 1987a: 86, note 1). I then remarked that the variants are perhaps ecologically determined, pointing to populations from Katanga, where individuals from dry deciduous forest (muhulu) approach the Guinean variant. The ecological amplitude of *T. coriacea* seems extremely wide, and the species even occurs on maritime sand (Banana, Bequaert 757, BR0000006423568).

In my 1987 revision I therefore concluded that a sole species is at stake, and only separated a subspecies (subsp. *angustifolia* (Garcia) Robbr.) for rheophytic narrow-leaved populations from the mountain ranges on the border of Zimbabwe and Mozambique. Yet I noticed (Robbrecht 1987a: 87, note 3) the existence of intermediate specimens in the localities where the subspecies overlaps with the rest of the populations. Also narrow leaved specimens from scattered localities are observed throughout the area (e.g. RD Congo, J. Léonard 589, BR0000009934917), and many such ones were collected in the recent decades (e.g. from Cameroon, Equatorial Guinea and Gabon); it is unlikely that these have a direct relationship with the stenophyllous populations from the southernmost part of the distribution area. This is casting even more doubt on subsp. *angustifolia*. In her treatment for Flora Zambesiaca, Bridson (2003) accepted this narrow-leaved variant as the third subspecies but doubted the rheophytic nature.

The Zambezan populations were traditionally identified *Tricalysia nyassae*. Bridson (2003) reinstated this taxon at the subspecific level, using the diagnostic characters surveyed in table 2. It is obvious that the distinction between the subspecies is subtle.

Table 2. Diagnostic characters used by Bridson (2003) to distinguish subspecies in <i>Tricalysia coriacea</i> . Blank cells corresponding to data not mentioned by her.			
subspecies	<i>coriacea</i>	<i>nyassae</i>	<i>angustifolia</i>
leaf blade texture	somewhat thinner		
blade width		(1.8)2.8–8.5 cm	0.9–3.8(6.5) cm
blade shape		moderately wide to wide, occasionally narrow but then widest above the middle	narrow, or occasionally moderately wide, usually widest at the middle
blade apex	mostly distinctly acuminate	rounded or, more often, obtuse or shortly acuminate	
inflorescence	often less crowded		
“cupules” (calyculi)	not densely pubescent inside (rims apparently ciliate rather than fringed)	densely pubescent within, rim distinctly fringed or occasionally not	lacking projecting hairs at rim
corolla size	smaller [than in <i>nyassae</i>]	lobes 6-8 mm	lobes 4-6 mm
corolla lobe tips	glabrous or ciliate		
corolla colour	usually white	dull-pink, pale-rose pink, salmon-piked or cream-coloured, or pink fading to white	mostly white
filaments		2–2.5 mm	1.2–1.5 mm
anthers	shorter [than in <i>nyassae</i>]	5–7 mm	4–5 mm

Table 3 assembles the flower colour observations by collectors in BR. Pink flowers are concentrated in and around the *Flora Zambesiaca* area but also occur in “Lower Guinea”. The hypothesis that the pink flower colour is diagnostic for subsp. *nyassae* seems biased by observations focusing on *Flora Zambesiaca* area specimens. The coexistence of white and pink flowers in Katanga is documented by photo material of M. Schaijes with his specimens in the herbarium BR (his number 1052, BR0000008915818; 1486, BR0000008916143; 3011, BR0000008911483).

Table 3. Flower colour variation of <i>Tricalysia coriacea</i> (subsp. <i>coriacea</i> + subsp. <i>nyassae</i> in the sense of Bridson), according to notes of collectors in BR. Numbers are numbers of collections. Note that only a small half of the specimens is in flower, and that many collection labels lack colour observations.		
	white	pink, salmon etc.
Liberia to Ivory Coast	8	0
Cameroon & Gabon to R Congo	4	3
RD Congo District I	1	0
III	2	0
IV	3	0
V	2	0
VI	13	0
XI	5	6
Burundi	2	0
Tanzania	1	1
Angola & Zambia	1	11
Malawi	1	5
Zimbabwe & Mozambique	3	0

I remain convinced that a sound investigation of *T. coriacea*, e.g. phylogeographic, remains necessary for a good comprehension of the extremely wide variation within the species; the closely related *T. hensii* should best be included in such a study. For the purposes of the *Flore*, I have not distinguished infraspecific taxa.

9. A montane *Tricalysia* from mount Zawa (Upper Katanga), and its relation to *T. kivuensis* and *T. verdcourtiana*

Only a few *Tricalysia* species occur in the mountains of the Albertine Rift in the east of the *Flore* area, e.g. *T. vanroechoudtii* belonging to section *Ephedranthera*. In the core group of *Tricalysia* only *T. kivuensis* is montane. This species is endemic to the mountains of the Congo-Nile Ridge in Kivu (R.D. Congo), Rwanda and Burundi, from the western side of Lake Kivu to the northern tip of Lake Tanganyika (Robbrecht 1987b: map 1030). It is related to *T. verdcourtiana*, a montane species from Tanzania, Zambia and Malawi, occurring at elevations of about 2000 m. The two species have the stipular morphology in common: a short sheath is overtopped by a long needle-like glabrous awn. The differences between them are given in table 4. [A side note: In my revision I cited a specimen from the Nyika Plateau in Zambia (Dowsett-Lemaire 165, BR0000008490193) as belonging to *T. kivuensis*. It was reidentified *T. verdcourtiana* by the collector. The leaf-tips bear a short mucro indeed, so the redetermination is correct.]

Table 4. The <i>Tricalysia</i> specimen from mount Zawa compared to its putative relatives.			
	<i>T. kivuensis</i>	Delvaux 527 (Zawa)	<i>T. verdcourtiana</i>
leaf blades underneath	pubescent, especially midnerve & margins	glabrous except midnerve	glabrous except midnerve
mucro (prolongation of midnerve)	absent	very short (only 0.2 mm)	distinct
lateral nerves	4–6(–8)	6–8	(5–)7-8(10)
domatia	densely hairy, sometimes pitted	sparsely hairy	hairy, sometimes hairs around weak pits
calyx teeth	subulate or dentate	?	dentate
corolla	pubescent outside	?	pubescent outside
ovules/placenta	(2–)4–7	?	2–4
style	hairy except base	?	glabrous
stigmata	hairy	?	hairy
anthers	mostly barbate at tip	?	glabrous
latitude (°S)	01–04	07	09–12

In 1954 Jacques Delvaux collected vascular plants from mount Zawa (06° 51' S, 29° 36' E), an ill explored mountain in the extreme NE of the Upper Katanga District. Published information on the mount is scarce. Diderrich (1895) shortly reported that the mount has a plateau summit that “porte une haute futaie d’un port colossal.” Duvigneaud (1958, as “Nzawa”) cited a description of the vegetation by Delevoy & Robert (1935) : “Les arbres dominants, souvent munis de contreforts, se présentent rarement en massifs, mais ils étalent plutôt leurs cimes isolées, souvent vastes et denses, sur un sous-bois fourré d’arbustes, d’arbrisseaux et de lianes. A côté des essences paraissant endémiques, on y trouve un certain nombre de plantes rencontrées dans les galeries de la zone septentrionale du Katanga méridional (*Piptadenia*, *Entandophragma*, *Parinari*), ainsi que d’autres répandues jusque dans la forêt équatoriale (*Trema orientalis*). Les Mousses et Lichens sont abondants. La flore herbacée et frutescente des clairières se caractérise par la présence de maints types de facies analogues aux plantes des régions tempérées boréales (*Rubus*, *Aquilegia*, *Adiantum*, *Pteris* et autres fougères, ainsi que d’autres plantes rappelant les laiterons : orties, oxalis, graminées, mousses d’Europe).” Duvigneaud (op. cit.) considered this type of forest as intermediate between montane variants of muhulu and genuine montane forests.

A *Tricalysia* specimen is among Delvaux’s Zawa plants. I had not seen this number 527 (BR0000008906373) for my revision and identified it later as *T. cf. verdcourtiana*. Its stipules have the needle-like awns of the two species discussed here. Its leaves have a very short mucro and therein indeed match *T. verdcourtiana*. The material is in very young flower bud stage, not allowing to verify the hairiness of styles and anthers; see table 4 for a further comparison. Mount Zawa lies in between the areas of *T. kivuensis* and *T. verdcourtiana*. More knowledge of the Zawa population is crucial for a better understanding of the relationship between the two species. Perhaps they represent a single species with slight local variation. One should either not exclude the existence of a third montane species from Zawa. However, this mount is at present almost inaccessible because of the unstable political situation in the area (Pierre Meerts, personal communication September 2023). In the *Flore* treatment I consider the Delvaux collection as an uncertain record of *T. kivuensis*.

10. Reestablishment of *Tricalysia aurantiodora* (synonym *Tricalysia obstetrix*)

In my revision (Robbrecht 1987a: 135), *Tricalysia aurantiodora* described from R.D. Congo was considered to be a synonym of *T. oligoneura*. I did so with some hesitation because the inflorescences of the type collection (Dewèvre 569) are somewhat more condensed than in typical *T.*

oligoneura. I expressed this doubt in an annotation slip on the isotype (BR0000008381699), but published the synonymy without any comment. *T. aurantiadora* should, however, be reestablished and is even an older name available for *Tricalysia obstetrix*, a species from Gabon (Olivier Lachenaud, personal communication 2022). Hallé (1970) described *T. obstetrix* stressing the brown colour of the leaves in the dry state and the morphology of the calyx with long subulate lobes (“à lobes digités aigus érigés, subégaux ou un peu inégaux de 1,8 à 2,5 mm de longueur”) as diagnostic characters. New collections became available from Gabon, and these show that the calyx lobes vary from long and subulate as in the type of *T. obstetrix* to shortly dentate as in the type of *T. aurantiadora*. The abrupt transition of the leaf-blade tips into a short acumen is a further characteristic shared by the Gabonese and Congolese materials.

De Wildeman (1903) described *Tricalysia aurantiadora* in his studies on plants from Katanga, and that could cause biogeographical objections against the proposed synonymy. However, De Wildeman included this equatorial species next to another *Tricalysia* species from Katanga (“Nous décrivons ci-dessous une autre espèce du même genre, bien qu’elle n’appartienne pas à la flore du Katanga.”)

11. The delimitation of *Tricalysia yangambiensis*

Tricalysia yangambiensis (N.Hallé) Robbr. was originally described as *Tricalysia soyauxii* K.Schum. var *yangambiensis* N.Hallé, based on a single Louis collection from Yangambi. During my revision it appeared that much more and better material from Yangambi was available, and this allowed me to demonstrate that the variety deserved recognition at the species level (for details, see Robbrecht 1987a: 107, table 2). Some easy spot characters were not stressed by me at that time: part of the leaves have elongated blades with parallel outer margins, petioles are up to 15 mm long, and flowering is abundant on leafless older twigs. The species remained, however, imperfectly known because only flowering material was collected. *T. yangambiensis* appeared to be restricted to Yangambi and surroundings. The only other then cited collection (Lebrun 5597, BR0000008906311), according to the label comes from Urega in the Maniema. This specimen is not shown on the distribution map (Robbrecht 1987b: map 1035), because the locality is not known with sufficient precision: “Urega” is indeed a region situated from 27° to 28° E and 1°30' to 3°30' S. The label notes that the collection was made at 1200 m, i.e. much higher than the c. 470 m elevation at Yangambi.

I also recognized a closely related species “sp. 49” on six poor specimens with flower buds or not fully mature fruits only (Robbrecht 1987a: 78). They represented a good morphological match of *T. yangambiensis*, with somewhat smaller leaves. Chorologically and ecologically, sp. 49 differs from *T. yangambiensis* in occurring in the (sub)montane forest types towards the NE of the Central forest District, as well as in the adjacent Lakes Edward and Kivu District, up to 1800 m elevation. The fruiting collections showed that the fruits are somewhat larger than in most *Tricalysia* spp., and have a leathery to sclerotic rather than a fleshy pericarp, suggesting that sp. 49 belongs to the *Tricalysia atherura* group, that is otherwise comprised of Lower Guinean species only.

Troupin 3414 (BR0000008903082) from Irangi, collected at 850–900 m elevation, was not cited in my 1987 revision. I already identified it in 1987 (i.e. shortly after the publication of my revision) as *T. yangambienis*, after having doubted whether it was not a collection of *T. pallens*, a very common species of *Tricalysia* that co-occurs at Irangi. With regard to locality and elevation, this specimen interestingly is intermediate between sp. 49 and *T. yangambiensis*.

In my revision, I stated that sp. 49 also differs from *T. yangambiensis* by having glabrous instead of puberulous ovaries. This is erroneous. The hairiness of the ovaries may be very delicate and can

hardly be observed in rehydrated herbarium material. In the *Flore* treatment I included sp. 49 in *T. yangambiensis*.

If the belonging of *T. yangambiensis* to the *Tricalysia atherura* group is confirmed, the flowers and fruits are definitely smaller than in most other species of that group. Herein, it only compares with *T. achoundongiana* and *T. vadensis* (Sonké et al. 2002).

12. *Tricalysia niamniamensis*: var. or subsp. *nodosa*?

In my revision of *Tricalysia* (Robbrecht 1987a) I replaced the once wide concept of *T. angolensis* (e.g. in White 1962) by three species, closely related but geographically more or less separated. Next to *T. angolensis* I used the available names *T. griseiflora* and *T. niamniamensis*. *T. angolensis* is easily set apart in being an obligate geofrutex with very narrow leaf blades, restricted to a small part of Bié (western Angola). *T. griseiflora* is a western Zambeian species, characterized by glabrous ovaries, blackish in the dried state, contrasting with the silvery pubescent calyx; corollas hairy inside; intersecondary nerves very apparent above. *T. niamniamensis* is an eastern Zambeian species, towards the north reaching South Sudan, characterized by pubescent ovaries, with at most the extreme base glabrous, thus not contrasting with the pubescent calyx; corolla tube glabrous inside; intersecondary nerves hardly distinguishable.

Table 5. Bridson's distinction of two subspecies in <i>Tricalysia niamniamensis</i> .		
	Subsp. <i>niamniamensis</i>	Subsp. <i>nodosa</i>
Leaves	Spaced along stems, blades not markedly dimorphic, often larger	Clustered at stem apex, dimorphic
Pairs of lateral nerves	(4–)5–6	4
petioles	Not markedly slender	Proportionally long
stipules	Somewhat larger	Limbs 1–1.5 mm Awns 0.5–1 mm
Corolla tube	6–7.5 mm long, exceeding the lobes	2.5–3 mm, subequal to lobes
Corolla lobes	4–5 x 2–3 mm, shortly or distinctly acuminate	2,5–3 x 1.25–1.5 mm, truncate or slightly emarginate

In both *T. griseiflora* and *T. niamniamensis*, I recognized three varieties. Nomenclaturally, this treatment was conservative because I judged that this group needs at any event and in-depth biosystematic approach (which we are still awaiting more than three decades later). Bridson (2003) followed my treatment of this group in her treatment for Flora Zambesiaca, except for *T. niamniamensis* var. *nodosa*. She considered that the morphological differences used by me – habit of the shrubs, shapes and hairiness of leaf-blades – are due to non-genetic factors (environment etc.) and raised var. *nodosa* to subspecies, also emending its diagnostic features and circumscription. She united all eastern Flora Zambesiaca material (Zambia E, Zimbabwe, Malawi, Mozambique) in subsp. *nodosa* [material from Zambia N, B, W of the Flora Zambesiaca area belongs to one of the two varieties of *T. griseiflora*]. Table 5 surveys her distinction between the two subspecies. Note that she made no comments on my third taxon, var. *djurensis* with cordate or rounded leaf-blades and reported from the *Flore* area. For the purpose of the *Flore* I have therefore kept my division in three varieties and their delimitation.

13. Intraspecific variation of *Tricalysia longituba*

Tricalysia longituba has a relatively wide distribution, from Cameroon and the Central African Republic to Angola and Zambia (Robbrecht 1982b: map 761). It is a linking element of the Guineo-Congolian and the Zambezi Region, though it is absent from the centre of the former, i.e. Gabon and the lowermost parts of the Congo basin. Its distribution shows no discontinuities and can be qualified as “pericongolian”. A relatively wide morphological variation goes hand in hand with this wide distribution. In my revision (Robbrecht 1982a) I separated var. *velutina* for some R.D. Congo specimens with leaf-blades softly velvety underneath. With regard to var. *longituba* I noted some geographical separation between collections from north of the Equator with mostly puberulous twigs and petioles and more southern material with mostly glabrous twigs and petioles. I refrained from formally recognizing these variants because of exceptions and intermediate collections, e.g. in Katanga.

Bridson (2003) did not follow this and proposed a subspecies *richardsiae* for the material from Tanzania, Katanga and Zambia. Her diagnosis mainly is based on overlapping characters. She noted the following characters of subspecies *longituba* (in her sense) absent from specimens from Katanga, Zambia and Tanzania (her subsp. *richardsiae*):

- (1) young stems brown (rarely buff), puberulous-pubescent;
- (2) leaf-blades obovate with apical acumen up to 2 cm long with rounded bases;
- (3) stigma/pollen presenter arms included well within the corolla tube (i.e. short-styled flowers);
- (4) fruits ellipsoid.

I compared this with the material from the area of the *Flore*. The leaf blade variation (2) in the material from the Central Forest District is wide, there are indeed specimens (e.g. Evrard 3731, BR 000009938304) with larger blades with rounded base and longer acumen. Other Central Forest District specimens (e.g. Louis 14151, BR0000019684666) have leaves matching Katanga material. With regard to (4), fruits of *T. longituba* are rarely collected. But the ellipsoid to spindle-shaped fruit (illustrated in Robbrecht 1982a: fig. 4) is in the northern, Guineo-Congolian collections more rare than the globose fruit thought to characterize subsp. *richardsiae*.

With regard to (1) and (3) I here include the evidence in the form of maps depicting the distribution of variation, prepared during my 1982 revision but kept unpublished then (note that hardly more specimens became available since my revision, so there is no possibly more detailed view). Fig. 8 (left) shows that the glabrous and the puberulous variant and intermediates co-exist in Upper Katanga.

It appears that the long-styled and short-styled floral morphs do not occur together (fig. 8, right). This should rather be seen as an expression of a general phenomenon in sect. *Ephedranthera*, viz. to “lose” one of the floral morphs. In *T. vanroechoudtii*, another species occurring in the area of the *Flore*, only the longistylous morph is observed despite the fact that the species is well-collected. In five other species (not in the *Flore* area, e.g. *T. elegans*) only the short-styled morph is collected. It seems that in *T. longituba* this “loss” is happening in parts of the area. Field studies are needed for a better comprehension of the floral biological adaptations in these species of *Tricalysia*.

In conclusion, there is no convincing evidence to accept subsp. *richardsiae*, and I have not done so in the *Flore*.

The specimen Dhetchuvi 1111 (BR0000009938199) from Botsima, made in 1991, indicates that further collecting is necessary for fully comprehending the variation of *Tricalysia longituba*. Botsima lies N of the “Parc National de la Salonga – Nord” in the heart of the lowland forest of the Congo basin. The area is poorly explored, and represents a gap in the known distribution area of *Tricalysia longituba*. Dhetchuvi 1111 has the characteristic flowers of the brevistylous morph of *Tricalysia longituba*, but deviates in having much more slender inflorescences, with longer and thinner pedicels and more narrow corolla tubes (see table 6). It might represent a separate taxon.

Table 6. Dhetchuvi 1111 compared to other material of <i>Tricalysia longituba</i> .		
	<i>Tricalysia longituba</i> var. <i>longituba</i>	Dhetchuvi 1111
peduncle	2–3 mm	7 mm
pedicels	up to 10(13) mm	14–16 mm
corolla tube	12–19 x 1–5 mm	15 x 1–2 mm wider where stigmata are included
corolla lobes	8–11 x 4–5 mm	4–5 x 3 mm
anthers	5–6.5 mm medifixed	10–11 mm supramedifixed

14. *Argocoffeopsis rupestris*

Plate 46 A in the *Flore* is taken from De Wildeman (1912: pl. 32, page 157) who published it as *Coffea divaricata* K.Schum. The latter species, with syntypes from Togo, is now a synonym of *A. rupestris* subsp. *rupestris*. The plate was drawn by Josef Fleischmann, an Austrian biological illustrator. His plates illustrating Congo seed plants were made in Vienna and drawn from specimens collected by Thonner (Thonner 1910), before the latter donated them to BR (see Lawalrée 1998). The plate hence without doubt represents subsp. *thonneri*, near-endemic to R.D. Congo, not subsp. *rupestris*, which occurs from Guinea to Nigeria.

Cheek et al. (2018: S1 Appendix) unintentionally (Larridon pers. comm. Nov. 2021) published the combination *Argocoffeopsis thonneri* (Lebrun) Larridon. Their molecular results indicated that

Argocoffeopsis rupestris subsp. *thonneri* (Lebrun) Robbr. is sister to *A. eketensis* while *Argocoffeopsis rupestris* subsp. *rupestris* is sister to *A. subcordata*. This is not in accordance with morphological data because the three taxa *eketensis*, *rupestris* and *thonneri* are the only deciduous ones in *Argocoffeopsis*. The molecular results, however, are based on very limited sampling (one collection for each of deciduous taxa, and only two more for the evergreen *Argocoffeopsis* taxa). The two subspecies have a vicariant distribution and are morphologically very close. I was unable to find morphological criteria for separation *rupestris* and *thonneri* at specific level. Keeping the subspecific status seems the best option at present, and I have done so in the *Flore*.

15. The genus *Psilanthus* kept separate from *Coffea*

Davis et al. (2007) provided molecular as well as morphological analyses of the Coffeae; these supported three suprageneric clades, among these a clade comprising *Coffea* and *Psilanthus*. Inside this clade these two genera were not monophyletic, however. The *Psilanthus* clade indeed comprised *Coffea kapakata*, rendering *Coffea* paraphyletic. These authors therefore suggested to place *Psilanthus* in synonymy with *Coffea*, despite the striking morphological and anatomical differences between the two genera. The necessary formal nomenclatural transfers were made a few years later (Davis 2010, 2011).

In the *Flore*, the two genera are kept separate, based on more recent molecular work. The genera are easily keyed out mainly by characters of the flowers (styles and stigmata included in *Psilanthus* and exerted in *Coffea*). In fruiting stage too, features of the calyx and colours allow to distinguish the genera. Molecular studies published after the work of Davis et al. indeed corroborated the existence of a *Psilanthus* clade next to a *Coffea* clade (Hamon et al. 2017, Guyeux et al. 2019, Charr et al. 2020). These papers placed *Coffea kapakata* in the *Coffea* clade, questioning hence the paraphyletic nature of *Coffea* postulated by Davis et al. However, these studies also revealed that another *Coffea* species not sampled before is sister to or nested in the *Psilanthus* clade; this concerns *Coffea rhamnifolia* from NE Africa, a xerophilic species first described as a separate genus *Paolia* (however, this generic recognition was based on the erroneous assumption that the taxon is related to *Feretia*, a member of the Octotropideae; see Bridson 1979). Next to their molecular evidence to distinguish *Psilanthus* from *Coffea*, Charr et al. (2020) enumerated morphological, architectural, anatomical and phytochemical supporting data. They proposed to place *Coffea rhamnifolia* either in *Psilanthus* or in a genus of its own, for which the name *Paolia* is available. They refrained from formally making one of these decisions because *C. rhamnifolia* remains ill known and poorly collected because its restricted occurrence is in hardly accessible war-torn regions. In the *Flore*, *Coffea* and *Psilanthus* are kept separate.

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